

CONCENTRATION OF COMBINED ASCORBIC ACID IN NORMAL URINE AND
THE IDENTIFICATION OF ITS ASCORBIC ACID COMPONENT VIA THE
2 : 4-DINITROPHENYLHYDRAZINE DERIVATIVE

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The combined ascorbic acid in the urine of normal persons has been concentrated and the 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine derivative of this ascorbic acid complex has been identified with the dinitrophenylhydrazine derivative obtained from ascorbic acid.

Existence of combined ascorbic acid in normal urine was reported by Scarborough and Stewart (*Biochem. J.*, 1937, 31, 2231) and by Guha and Sengupta (*Nature*, 1938, 141, 972). Further observations on urinary ascorbic acid have been made by Banerjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 463) and Sengupta (*Ann. Biochem. Expt. Med.*, 1941, 1, 219). Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 16, 241, 657) observed that the excretion of combined ascorbic acid in the urine of the guinea-pig was increased when injected with sublethal doses of diphtheria and tetanus toxins, and suggested the possibility of ascorbic acid combining with certain products of metabolites as a result of infection. Similar increase of combined ascorbic acid in the urine of tubercular patients has been observed by Banerjee, Sen and Guha (*Nature*, 1940, 145, 706; *Ann. Biochem. Expt. Med.*, 1941, 1, 27). Banerjee and Guha (*Ann. Biochem. Expt. Med.*, 1942, 2, 125) have observed the disappearance of combined ascorbic acid in the urine of normal persons as well as in the urine of tubercular patients, when administered with large doses of pure ascorbic acid.

The presence of combined ascorbic acid in the normal urine, its increase during infection and its disappearance when the body is saturated with ascorbic acid, suggest the possible function of ascorbic acid in the process of detoxication. The disappearance of combined ascorbic acid from the normal urine might perhaps indicate an optimum intake of vitamin-C, though this would not probably correspond to saturation of the body (Banerjee and Guha, *loc. cit.*).

Recently Ahmad, Qureshi, Toosy and Babbar (*Ann. Biochem. Expt. Med.*, 1945, 5, 81) have confirmed our findings of the presence of combined ascorbic acid in normal urine and its increase under pathological conditions. The nature of this combined ascorbic acid in the urine is still unknown. Investigations were carried out in this laboratory to throw light on the chemical nature of combined ascorbic acid.

The present investigation provides further evidence about the existence of combined ascorbic acid in normal human urine. A fair amount of concentration of combined ascorbic acid has been identified as its 2 : 4-dinitrophenylhydrazine derivative.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sengupta (*loc. cit.*) observed that combined ascorbic acid in the urine was sufficiently stable and its splitting required one of the following drastic treatments, namely, (i) sufficient lowering of p_H below 1.6 and hydrolysis on a boiling water-bath for 1 hour in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide, (ii) reduction by hydrogen sulphide on a boiling water-

bath for 15 minutes (*cf.* Sengupta and Guha, *loc. cit.*), and (iii) by prolonged treatment with hydrogen sulphide (Scarborough and Stewart, *loc. cit.*) or reduction by stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid and subsequent hydrolysis in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide (Meiklelohn and Stewart, *Biochem. J.*, 1941, 35, 761).

Sufficient quantities of urine were collected from several healthy persons and were acidified with glacial acetic acid so as to obtain 5% concentration. Aliquots of urine (100 c.c.) were subjected to the following examinations:—

- (i) Amounts of free, dehydro- and combined ascorbic acids in the original sample.
- (ii) Amounts of free, dehydro- and combined ascorbic acids remaining in the urine after keeping it for 24 hours in a refrigerator.
- (iii) Amounts of free, dehydro- and combined ascorbic acids remaining in the urine after shaking with 1% concentration of norit charcoal.
- (iv) Amounts of free, dehydro- and combined ascorbic acids left in charcoal-treated urine when kept in the refrigerator for 24 to 72 hours.

TABLE I

No. of Expt.	Nature of urine.	Mg. of indophenol reducing materials calculated in terms of ascorbic acid per 100 c.c. of urine.		
		Free.	Dehydro.	Combined.
I	Original	0.80	0.02	0.60
II	Charcoal treated	0.00	0.65	0.60
III	Original urine kept in refrigerator for 24 hours	0.65	0.15	0.60
IV	Charcoal treated urine kept in refrigerator for 24 hours	0.00	0.65	0.60
V	Charcoal treated urine kept in refrigerator for 72 hours	0.00	0.65	0.60

It will be observed from Table I that the combined ascorbic acid in the urine remained unadsorbed by charcoal. The yellow colour of the urine was, however, removed completely.

About 600 c.c. of acidified and charcoal-treated urine were evaporated under vacuum on a boiling water-bath with a view to concentrating the combined ascorbic acid in the urine. The urine was evaporated to about 65 c.c. and was taken in a receiver where on cooling glacial acetic acid was added to bring the volume exactly to 70 c.c. Portions (10 c.c.) of the above concentrated urine were estimated for the presence of free, dehydro- and combined ascorbic acids initially present after charcoal treatment and after concentration and subsequent charcoal treatment. The keeping property of the combined ascorbic acid remained unaffected when kept in the refrigerator for 24 and 72 hours. Results are tabulated in Table II.

TABLE II

Nature of urine.	Mg. of indophenol reducing substances calculated in terms of ascorbic acid per 100 c.c. of urine		
	Free.	Dehydro.	Combined.
Initially charcoal treated	0.00	3.90	3.60
Concentrated and charcoal treated	0.00	2.66	2.10
Above kept in refrigerator for 24 to 72 hours	0.00	2.66	2.10

It will be evident from Table II that about 58 % of the combined ascorbic acid remained as such during the process of concentration in *vacuo*.

10 Litres of urine were evaporated by the process described above and the volume was made up to 600 c.c. with sufficient acetic acid. The urine thus concentrated was shaken with norit charcoal for 3 to 4 times to get a clear liquid which remained light yellow in colour. Aliquots (20 c.c. each) of the concentrated urine were subjected to the following treatments and in each case the amount of indophenol reducing materials as originally present and formed after treatment with cold and hot hydrogen sulphide, were noted. A 20 c.c. aliquot weighed about 25 g. On complete evaporation of a second aliquot the solid mass weighed 10 g. and the reducing materials present were determined. From a third aliquot, the solid mass was extracted with absolute alcohol in order to remove the unnecessary salts which remained in the evaporated urine concentrate. The extraction was repeated twice for complete extraction. The unnecessary salts remaining after alcoholic extraction weighed 4 g. The alcoholic extract was evaporated in vacuum on a boiling water-bath. The pasty mass obtained after the evaporation of the alcohol gradually set to a solid mass if kept in cold inside a refrigerator. The mass weighed 6 g. and was dissolved in water and its reducing capacity was determined. The results are recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

Aliquot No.	Weight.	Mg. of indophenol reducing substances expressed in terms of ascorbic acid per 100 c.c. urine.		
		Free.	Dehydro.	Combined.
I (first)	25 g.	0.104	1.31	1.39
II (second)	10	0.88	1.42	1.28
III (third)	6	0.43	0.80	1.03

The mass derived from the evaporation of the alcoholic extract contained a lot of salts. Apart from the salts, the amounts of indophenol reducing substances have been estimated by the use of the enzyme, ascorbic acid oxidase, (oxidation method already described); Ghosh, *loc. cit.*). Salts were removed by dialysis. The mass obtained by the method described above, was dissolved in 2.5 % acetic acid solution and dialysed in a cellophane chamber. The dialysate contained 80 c.c. of the same 2.5% acetic acid solution. The whole process of the dialysis was carried out for a period of 24 to 26 hours inside a refrigerator maintained at a temperature near about $\pm 4-6^{\circ}$. The liquid inside the cellophane was found to have increased and became lighter in colour. The outer liquid developed yellow colour. The amounts of reducing materials and the amounts of true ascorbic acid, present inside the cellophane chamber as well as in the outside, were determined. The results in Table IV give the comparative values of the non-specific reducing substances and true ascorbic acid present in the urine concentrate before and after dialysis. The liquid remained inside the cellophane chamber contained ascorbic acid only in the combined form and was devoid of free and dehydroascorbic acids.

TABLE IV

State and amounts of indophenol reducing materials and true ascorbic acid present in concentrated urine corresponding to 100 c.c. urine

A. Before dialysis				True ascorbic acid (ascertained by enzymic oxidation method)			
Reducing materials in the forms as derived by treatment with cold and hot hydrogen sulphide				Total.	Free.	Dehydro.	Combined.
Total.	Free	Dehydro.	Combined.				
1.44	0.30	0.35	0.79	0.74	0.05	0.30	0.39
B. After dialysis							
			(i) Outside the cellophane chamber				
0.40	0.147	0.107	0.15	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.07
			(ii) Inside the cellophane chamber				
0.00	0.30	0.00	0.00	0.30

The liquid inside the cellophane chamber yielded on evaporation a small amount of solid and showed the presence of salts still remaining undialysed. Further dialysis at this stage was not carried out. 2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazine derivative was prepared at this stage to identify the ascorbic acid component of the combined ascorbic acid present in this dialysed urine. The method employed in the preparation of the dinitrophenylhydrazine derivative was slightly modified from the methods described by Herbert, Hist, Percival, Reynold and Smith (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1270), Roe and Hall (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1939, 128, 329) and Damm, Scarborough and Stewart (*Biochem. J.*, 1937, 31, 1874).

Pure ascorbic acid supplied by Hofmann la Roche was dissolved in a 2.5% acetic acid solution. An equal volume of a saturated solution of 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine hydrochloride in 2.5% chemically pure hydrochloric acid was added to the ascorbic acid solution and then 5 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid were added to the above mixture. The mixture was then warmed for 2-4 minutes on a boiling water-bath and was kept in a thermostat adjusted at 40° for 24-40 hours. The precipitate thus obtained was allowed to remain in contact with the solution for a further period of 2 days. The precipitate was then washed after filtration with distilled water to remove excess of hydrochloric acid. By following the similar procedure the dinitrophenylhydrazine derivative from the dialysed urine inside the cellophane chamber was obtained. The precipitate formed from the dialysed urine was darker in colour and the colour remained almost unchanged even when once purified. About 10 mg. of 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine derivative were obtained by the above process from 25 litres of pooled human urine. The melting point of this dinitrophenylhydrazine derivative lies between 250° and 258°, while the dinitrophenylhydrazine derivative obtained from pure ascorbic acid melted at 268-270°. The dinitrophenylhydrazine derivative of the dialysed urine cannot be purified further due to the small amount of the material derived.

My best thanks are due to Dr. B. C. Guha for his keen interest and placing the resources of his laboratory at my disposal to carry out this investigation.